

SECTION OF CHEMICAL SCIENCES

BUILDING CERAMICS BASED ON ASH AND SLAG WASTE

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Abstract

The results of research on the influence of ash-slag and wood waste, as well as surfactants on the properties of ceramic masses are presented. It is shown that complex activation of ash-slag ceramic mass by corrective additives in the form of surfactants leads to a decrease in molding humidity and improvement of physical and mechanical properties of ceramics with simultaneous reduction of firing temperature by 50-100°C.

Keywords: ceramic composition, surfactants, ashes and slags of thermal power plants, sawdust, effective ceramics.

Introduction

Extraction and processing of natural mineral raw materials are associated with the formation of a large number of various industrial wastes, the accumulation of which leads to a deterioration of the environmental situation in the regions. In this connection the problem of application in ceramic materials of industrial wastes acquires special urgency [6].

The vast majority of waste is silicates, and therefore a valuable raw material for the building materials industry and for building ceramics, in particular [7]. Thus, about 100 billion tons of various wastes accumulated in dumps and storages on the territory of Kazakhstan, which sharply aggravated the environmental situation. Therefore, the problem of waste disposal has been particularly acute in recent years [1].

Among industrial waste, one of the first places in terms of the volume of dumps is occupied by ash and slag from the combustion of solid fuels. The increased chemical activity of these products in comparison with materials that have not undergone heat treatment makes it possible to reduce fuel and energy costs by more than a third during their subsequent use in the production of building materials and products. [4]

In this work, special attention was focused on obtaining wall ceramics with improved physical and mechanical characteristics by modification of ceramic mass from plastic clay raw materials in composition with ash and slag from thermal power plants, as well as with surfactants.

Currently, in the whole country, no more than 5-10% [3] of ash and slag material is disposed of in various sectors of construction and industry. The remainder is stored in ash and slag dumps without use. At the same time, the accumulation of ash and slag does not stop,

and taking into account the growing demand for electricity and the insufficient pace of development of other sources of its production, the increase in the amount of stored ash and slag waste will increase. Ash and slag materials in chemical and mineralogical composition are largely identical to natural mineral raw materials. Their use in industry, the construction industry and agriculture is one of the strategic ways to solve the environmental problem in the area of operation of the TPP. The use of ash and slag from TPP plants in the production of building materials, including wall ceramics, is reflected in many works [2, 5, 8, 9].

In connection with the above, the purpose of this work is to develop compositions for the production of building ceramics based on mineral and organic industrial waste to ensure the required physical and mechanical characteristics. The use of ash and slag from thermal power plants makes it possible to solve not only the problems of resource conservation through waste disposal, but also issues of environmental protection from man-made pollution and the production of effective wall ceramics.

Materials and methods

On the basis of the analysis of the technology of effective wall ceramics the introduction of industrial wastes (ashes and slags of TPP) and modifiers in the form of surfactants (superplasticizer "Polyplast SP-1") into the composition of the raw material charge is accepted, which are more technological, having simultaneously polyfunctional influence on the molding properties of the clay mass, drying properties of the raw material, as well as operational properties of ceramics after firing.

Determination of technological properties of raw material compositions was carried out in accordance with GOST 21216-2014 "Raw clay material". Water

absorption and density of the fired samples were evaluated according to the methods of GOST 7025-91, strength – in accordance with GOST 530-2012. Thermal conductivity of the fired samples was determined using a portable electronic device ITP MG4.

In this work as clay components used clay from the quarry "Kazachye" of East Kazakhstan region, ash and slags of TPP of Ust-Kamenogorsk city.

Table 1

Physical and mechanical properties of clay from the Kazachye quarry in the East Kazakhstan region

Number of plasticity	Coefficient of sensitivity to drying	Air shrinkage, %	Molding humidity, %	Average density, g/cm ³
8.83	0.13	6	18	1.7

In terms of plasticity, clay is classified as a group of moderately plastic clay raw materials. The introduction of TPP ash into the composition of the ceramic mass significantly reduces its plasticity.

Ash and slag waste from Ust-Kamenogorsk TPP was used as a resource-saving additive.

Depending on the chemical composition according to the requirements of GOST 25818-2018, these wastes belong to the group of acidic raw materials containing CaO up to 10% by weight (Table 2).

Table 2

Chemical composition of ash, %

SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	Fe ₂ O ₃	NiO ₂	TiO ₂	CaO	MgO	MnO	Na ₂ O	K ₂ O	P ₂ O ₅	SO ₃
60.2	15.5	4.0	1.0	1.0	8.67	0.88	0.1	0.6	3.2	1.0	2.3

In most cases, pre-machining is used in the preparation of raw materials, including waste in the production of ceramic materials. In laboratory tests conducted at the International Educational Corporation (KazGASA), the raw materials were crushed in a ball mill and sieved through a sieve No 01. As practice has shown, such granulometry is considered the most optimal in the production of wall ceramics.

Results and discussion

To determine the optimal composition of the ceramic composition, cube samples with sizes 2*2 and 4*4 cm were formed. The samples were produced by

plastic molding using techniques adopted in the technology of ceramic materials. After sorting, the molded samples were pre-dried in a drying cabinet (SNOL-58/350) at a temperature of 110°C to a constant mass. The samples were fired in a muffle furnace (SNOL 8.2*1100) at each set temperature with an interval of 50°C with an exposure time of 15-20 minutes. The furnace was loaded at room temperature, unloading – no more than 60°C.

To carry out experimental work, compositions of ceramic masses were compiled in the ratios shown in Table 3.

Table 3

Compositions of ceramic compositions

Composition No	Composition of ceramic mass, %				
	Clay	Ash	Slag	Sawdust	Molding humidity, %
1	100	0	0	0	18
2	95	5	0	0	21.9
3	95	0	5	0	23
4	90	5	5	0	14.2
5	85	5	10	0	21.9
6	85	10	5	0	24
7	80	10	10	0	22
8	75	15	10	0	25
9	75	10	15	0	21.9
10	70	15	15	0	25.7

Table 4

Change in compressive strength of samples of different composition depending on the firing temperature, MPa

No	Composition: Clay / Ash / Slag	1000°C	1050°C	1100°C
1	100	10.36	14.04	13.73
2	95/5/0	9.68	12.62	14.1
3	95/0/5	8.47	12.83	15.2
4	90/5/5	8.2	12.5	14.7
5	85/5/10	6.29	12.8	16.9
6	85/10/5	6.8	13.71	17.8
7	80/10/10	9.5	14.4	17.81
8	75/15/10	7.02	8.78	12.3
9	75/10/15	5.19	8.07	11.24
10	70/15/15	4.13	7.85	10.1

The ash and slag content in the ceramic composition varied from 5 to 15%. A further increase in the ash content led to an increase in the molding humidity above 24%, therefore, to a decrease in the strength of the samples after firing.

According to the data obtained, when ash is added in an amount of 5% of the total mass of dry components, it allows the strength of the samples to be maintained within 8 MPa already at a temperature of 1050°C, with an increase in the firing temperature, the strength of the samples increases, respectively, 1050°C – 12.6 MPa, 1100°C – 14.1 MPa, which corresponds to the brand of brick M100-150.

The data in the table 4 and the shapes of the curves in Fig. 1 show that a ceramic shard with a strength of

13.73 MPa (composition 1) can be obtained from pure clay without any additives at a firing temperature of 1100°C. Analysis of changes in the physico-mechanical properties of heat-treated samples in the presence of a 5% slag additive in the composition showed an increase in strength already at a firing temperature of 1050°C to 12.83 MPa, and at 1100°C – 15.2 MPa (composition 3). With the addition of ash and slag to clay up to 10%, the strength of the samples increased markedly: at 1000°C – up to 9.5 MPa, and at 1050°C the strength was increased to 11.4 MPa and at 1100°C a strength of 17.8 MPa was achieved (composition 7). Modification of the composition based on clay with ash and slag of the TPP made it possible to reduce the firing temperature by 50-100°C.

Figure 1. Change in compressive strength of samples of various compositions depending on the firing temperature, MPa

Analysis of changes in the properties of the studied samples depending on the percentage of components (data from Table 4 and Fig. 1) made it possible to optimize the compositions of the ceramic mass. The best indicators of physical and mechanical properties

were obtained as a result of firing samples from composite composition No. 7 (wt. %: clay-ash-slag : 80-10-10) was selected as optimal for subsequent studies in the presence of chemical additives.

Further research consisted in modifying the ceramic mass with sawdust (to reduce the density of products, Table 5).

Table 5

Physico-mechanical and drying properties of ceramic samples of the composition "clay - ash and slag of TPP - sawdust" before and after heat treatment

No	Component ratio: clay-ash-slag %	Sawdust, %	Molding humidity (absolute), %	Air shrinkage, %	Average density of raw material after drying, g/cm ³	Properties of samples at different firing temperatures, compressive strength R, water absorption by weight W, average density ρ					
						1050°C			1100°C		
						R, MPa	W, %	ρ , g/sm ³	R, MPa	W, %	ρ , g/sm ³
1a		5	25	2	1.76	8.61	27.1	1.15	10.86	24.5	1.16
2a	80-10-10	7	27.3	3	1.68	11.44	40.4	1.07	13.98	28.5	1.05
3a		10	29.8	2	1.62	3.05	57.6	1	5.66	45.7	0.98

Table 6

Physico-mechanical and drying properties of ceramic samples of the composition "clay – ash and slag of TPP – sawdust – superplasticizer" before and after firing

Composition No.	Ratio of components: clay-ash-slag-sawdust %	Superplasticizer (surfactant), %	Molding humidity (absolute), %	Air shrinkage, %	Average density of the raw samples, g/cm ³	Properties of samples at different firing temperatures, compressive strength R, water absorption by weight W, average density ρ					
						1050°C			1100°C		
						R, MPa	W, %	ρ , g/sm ³	R, MPa	W, %	ρ , g/sm ³
2b	80-10-10-7	0.5	32	4	1.72	8.91	46.2	1.13	5.1	25.1	1.14
2c	80-10-10-7	1	29.8	4	1.73	10.5	43.8	1.08	10.4	20.5	1.13
2d	80-10-10-7	2	28	4	1.68	13.92	37.1	1.08	14.7	23.9	1.1
2e	80-10-10-7	3	29	4	1.72	10.5	46.7	1.1	14.08	26	1.2
2g	80-10-10-7	5	27,3	2	1.71	13.4	47.2	1.13	14	40	1.16

According to the experimental data, the optimal composition was selected (Table 5, composition 2a), in which the samples had the highest strength. Next, experiments were carried out with surfactants (surfactants), which, in addition to the plasticizing effect, lead to a decrease in molding moisture (Table 6, composition 2d) and, consequently, to an increase in the brand of products.

Conclusion

1. The effectiveness of complex activation of ceramic mass has been experimentally confirmed, which improves the physical and mechanical characteristics of ceramic samples by modifying clay raw materials using ash and slag from TPP, sawdust in a composition with surfactants as additives: reduction of shrinkage, reduction of molding moisture, increase in the strength of samples.

2. The use of ash and slag from thermal power plants, sawdust allows to simultaneously solve the problems of resource conservation and environmental protection from man-made pollution, and also contributes to the production of effective wall ceramics.

3. It was found that a decrease in the molecular mobility of water in the presence of a chemical additive increases the fluidity of the mass, therefore, reduces the molding humidity.

4. The optimal composition of the ceramic composition containing clay – 80%, ash and slag of TPP – 10%, sawdust – 7% and up to 3% surfactants for the production of ceramic bricks by plastic molding has been determined. At the same time, a grade of at least M100-150 was achieved, samples belonging to the effective category ($\lambda= 0.38 \text{ W/m}^\circ\text{C}$) were obtained while reducing the firing temperature by 50-100°C.

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